

Annual Activity Report 2024/2025

Austrian Mandated Organization / EOSC
Support Office Austria

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Executive Summary

This Activity Report provides a comprehensive overview of the EOSC Support Office Austria's (EOSC SOA) work from July 2024 to June 2025, with comments on its alignment with the European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda (2022–2024). The report highlights EOSC SOA's role in supporting Austria's engagement with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and its evolving position within the broader European research landscape.

EOSC SOA closely followed the initial steps of the [EOSC Federation build-up phase](#), contributing to the Tripartite questionnaire in summer 2024, participating in webinars, and engaging in early dialogue meetings with shortlisted candidate nodes in December 2024. Further activities in this area intensified in July 2025, which falls outside the current reporting period.

Throughout the reporting period, the EOSC SOA experienced significant growth and increased visibility. The [General Assembly](#), hosted by the University of Vienna in December 2024, welcomed two new partners: the Vienna University of Economics and Business and the Ludwig Boltzmann Gesellschaft (LBG). Additional institutions, including EODC, BOKU, the University of Salzburg, and the Austrian Academy of Sciences (ÖAW), also joined, more than doubling the number of partners since 2021.

The [Steering Committee](#) met once during the reporting period, emphasizing the strategic importance of establishing an Austrian EOSC Node – initiating respective discussions in July 2025. While key performance indicators (KPIs) show strong progress, the committee identified the need for continued expansion of the Austrian EOSC community and sustainable funding to ensure long-term success as a National EOSC Node.

The [Management Board](#) decided to put this period's focus on Community Building and Stakeholder Engagement, regular updates on EOSC-related projects, and closely monitoring the development of EOSC Nodes.

The [Secretariat](#) played a central role in operational activities and outreach, co-organizing and participating in events, maintaining and expanding web content, publishing newsletters, facilitating knowledge sharing through formats such as "knowledge snacks", project reports and articles.

Two [Working Groups](#) achieved tangible outputs, including the submission of three peer-reviewed papers. The Researcher Engagement Working Group participated in conferences representing both their work and the broader mission of EOSC SOA.

Finally, the [EOSC Café](#) convened twice, providing a platform for dialogue on key topics such as the EOSC Federation Handbook and the role of Candidate Nodes, helping shape future directions in this evolving landscape.

Overall, the reporting period reflects a phase of strategic consolidation, community expansion, and active contribution to Austria's positioning within the EOSC.

Introduction

The EOSC Support Office Austria (EOSC SOA) serves as the central national coordination hub for Austria's engagement with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Established in 2021 it unites a diverse consortium that includes research-performing organizations (predominantly universities, museums, and others), research infrastructures, and ministerial partners. Through coordination, dialogue, and knowledge translation, EOSC SOA acts as a bridge between European EOSC developments and Austria's research community turning strategy into action and ensuring that national implementation is deeply embedded in the evolving European landscape. EOSC SOA aligns its national EOSC implementation strategy with Austria's European Research Area¹ (ERA) commitments, ensuring that its activities directly contribute to the ERA Policy Agenda 2022–2024.

The European Research Area (ERA) aims to create an internal market for knowledge in Europe, with free movement of researchers and exchange of scientific information. This goal was enshrined in the EU Lisbon Treaty (TFEU Art. 179²). In late 2021 EU Member States adopted a new ERA Policy Agenda for 2022–2024 (Council Conclusions of Nov. 2021) as part of the EU "Pact for Research and Innovation". This Agenda sets out 20 priority actions to make the European research and innovation (R&I) system fit for future challenges.

In this context, Austria prepared its national ERA Action Plan 2022–2025³. It is a national roadmap to implement the EU's ERA Policy Agenda 2022–2024. Its overarching goal is to further develop Austria's R&I system in line with common European priorities (regarding Open Science, researcher mobility and careers, knowledge valorization, green and digital transitions, etc.) by integrating national measures into the ERA framework.

The plan is structured into 12 national initiatives (chapters), each mapped to one or more ERA actions. These initiatives were developed through broad stakeholder consultations – involving universities, research institutions, funding bodies, social partners, and interest groups and reflect Austria's own R&I environment rather than strictly following the ERA Agenda's chapter structure⁴.

Under the Austrian ERA-NAP 2022–2025, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) represents a strategic priority anchored in Initiative 2.2: "Development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) – Austrian involvement", which directly addresses ERA Action 01 – the enablement of open sharing and reuse of research outputs through EOSC. This initiative commits Austria to a comprehensive national engagement with EOSC:

¹ ERA: <https://era.gv.at/era/>

² ELI: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/treaty/tfeu_2016/art_179/oj

³ Austrian Action Plan for the European Research Area (ERA-NAP) 2022-2025
https://era.gv.at/public/documents/4824/ERA-NAP_2022-2025_EN_final.pdf

⁴ For example: *Towards an Open Science* (Initiative 2.1) – addresses ERA Action 01 (*open sharing of knowledge/EOSC*) and Action 02 (*EU research copyright framework*). A comparison table in the plan maps each initiative to the relevant ERA actions.

establishing EOSC-compliant services, integrating Austrian data repositories and infrastructures into the EOSC Federation, and actively participating in the governance and operational frameworks of EOSC at the European level. These efforts form the backbone of Austria's coherent EOSC implementation strategy. Rather than pursuing isolated projects, Austria is pursuing a unified approach that encompasses governance, technical readiness, stakeholder collaboration, and international cooperation aligning with both EOSC's overarching goals and relevant ERA commitments.

The work of the EOSC Support Office Austria is particularly aligned with the following ERA Actions (and corresponding initiatives within the ERA-NAP 01, 02, 03, 06, 10):

- **ERA Action 1 – Open Science:** EOSC-SOA facilitates open knowledge sharing and reuse of research outputs, through its newsletter and website, the EOSC Café, stakeholder workshops.
- **ERA Action 8 – Research Infrastructures:** EOSC SOA supports resilient, accessible research data infrastructures by using targeted communication and collaborative governance.
- **ERA Action 13 – Digital Transformation:** EOSC SOA encourages Austria's research institutions in developing digital capacities by promoting trainings and capacity-building events to align national services and institutions with the goals of EOSC.

Through these activities, Austria is starting to develop a robust national EOSC infrastructure ecosystem that meets pan-European interoperability standards, supports Open Science and FAIR principles, and secures a strategic role in the broader EOSC Federation.

The following report details the activities and organizational efforts of the EOSC SOA from July 2024 to June 2025. It outlines the work over the past year across three interconnected dimensions. First, it provides an overview of the activities related to the EOSC Federation build-up phase. It then moves on to detail governance and community coordination, showcasing the roles of the General Assembly, Steering Committee, Management, and Secretariat, reporting on communication and stakeholder engagement, including events and workshops. Eventually, the report highlights the outcomes of the Workings Groups and of the EOSC Café sessions aimed at fostering dialogue. Together, these activities paint a comprehensive picture of EOSC SOA activities and structured contribution to the EOSC implementation and information exchange.

Activities July 2024 - June 2025

Activities related to the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation

The activities of the EOSC Tripartite Governance in the initial steps of building the EOSC Federation were followed very closely by the EOSC SOA, with particular attention to the process outlined by the EOSC Association⁵. EOSC SOA contributed to the questionnaire launched in summer 2024 and participated in several webinars organized by the EOSC Association to present the expectations and requirements for candidate nodes.

In December 2024, EOSC SOA was shortlisted as a candidate node and invited to participate in the first dialogue meetings with the Tripartite Governance. After presenting EOSC SOA at the first meeting in December 2024 and following intensive discussions with ACONET Verein, a joint decision was reached not to engage in the first wave of the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation. In this context, the perspectives of EOSC SOA were continuously represented in the Tripartite process and the implications for Austria carefully assessed.

Following discussions at the EOSC Café meeting on 8 April 2025 further preparatory steps towards possibly establishing an EOSC Austrian Node were discussed. A first meeting was convened (outside the current reporting period) on 11 July 2025 at TU Wien⁶, greatly intensifying discussions and preparations for the potential establishment of an Austrian EOSC Node.

General Assembly

The fourth EOSC SOA General Assembly, held in December 2024, was hosted by the University of Vienna, a key partner of the EOSC SOA initiative. This event brought together leading figures to discuss the progress and future direction of EOSC in Austria. Notable international guest speakers from the Czech Republic and the EOSC Association, along with representatives from the EOSC SOA and experts in Science and Technology Studies (STS), contributed valuable insights. The General Assembly underscored the continued expansion of the EOSC initiative, highlighting the strength of its extensive network at both national and international levels. A comprehensive report on the EOSC SOA General Assembly is available on Zenodo⁷.

During the General Assembly, two new EOSC SOA Partners were welcomed: Vienna University of Economics and Business and the Ludwig Boltzmann Gesellschaft (LBG). Additionally, the EODC, the BOKU, the University of Salzburg as well as the ÖAW joined the EOSC SOA during the 2024/25 reporting period, further strengthening the initiative's growing community.

⁵ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about/building-the-eosc-federation/contributing-to-the-build-up-phase/>
https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/EOSC-Federation_First-Stage-Dialogue_Briefing-questionnaire_Tripartite_due_20250107.pdf

⁶ <https://eosc-austria.at/talks-underway-toward-an-austrian-eosc-node/>

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/14677563>

The next EOSC SOA General Assembly will be held on 18 November 2025 at TUtheSky, hosted by TU Wien, a founding partner of the EOSC SOA initiative.

Beyond the GA meeting itself, there was intensive contact between the representatives, enabling activities to foster the evolution and development of EOSC in Austria. This encompassed, in collaboration across the various bodies of the Support Office Austria, activities such as engaging with the EOSC Tripartite Governance during the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation; participating in webinars organized by the EOSC Association on the progress of the build-up phase and related opportunities; informing national stakeholders; representing and presenting the EOSC Support Office Austria (EOSC SOA) in various exchange meetings with other Mandated Organizations; coordinating efforts in the preparatory phase towards the establishment of an EOSC Austrian Node; and exploring opportunities to join project consortia focused on EOSC national node topics.

Steering Committee

In the reporting period, the Steering Committee focused on the build-up phase of the EOSC node concept and, therefore, met on 8 November 2024 at TU Wien Library, after the launch of the EOSC EU Node at the EOSC Symposium in Berlin. The members of the Steering Committee recommended a meeting with all partners and other stakeholders from outside the SOA to discuss the following points for the transformation of the EOSC SOA towards an EOSC National Node:

Figure 1: EOSC-KPIs: Objectives at the SOA-level. CC-BY, credits: Beate Guba (concept), and Juliana de Mello Castro Giroletti (graphic).

- Requirements for EOSC Nodes
- Strengthening proven structures
- New business models, technical challenges and knowledge exchange
- Role of the EOSC SOA Secretariat
- Working Groups needed in the transformation phase

In coordination with other EOSC SOA bodies, members of the Steering Committee contributed to the workshop held on 11 July 2025 as described in "Activities related to the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation". The involvement of stakeholders from outside the SOA will follow in the process. As a strategic body, the Steering Committee intends to review the proposal for the Austrian Node Candidacy developed by a core group of EOSC SOA partners and make recommendations on it.

The Steering Committee reviews the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of the Austrian EOSC Initiative developed by the KPIs Working Group on a yearly basis (see Figure 1 and Figure 2). These indicators demonstrate a very positive development, but strategically expanding the Austrian EOSC community, and securing sustainable funding from the ministry for the operations remain pivotal to becoming a National EOSC Node.

	Objectives	Indicators	Methods	Types of institutions	Data collection frequency	Source of data	Dissemination channels		Status 12/24	
							Internal	External		
	Community Building We align institutions through our Austrian EOSC partnership and implement support in our institutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> partners of EOSC SOA EOSC reference points in partner institutions research support activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of signatories of the MoU number of reference points (headcounts) number of workshops, webinars, engagement activities 	all types	1 x per year	Management Board (Chairperson)	• colAB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> website newsletter Austria Country Profile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 7 ordinary partners 9 extraordinary partners 22 EOSC reference points in these institutions 3 webinars, 3 conference participations, 1 summer school, 1 Erasmus exchange, 2 papers 	↑
	Coordination The EOSC Support Office Austria coordinates the national partnership efficiently.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> standardised processes transparent voting processes regular meetings Back office staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> review of processes and structures frequency of internal meetings number of back office staff in FTEs 	all types	Evaluation period April 2023	Management Board (Chairperson)	• colAB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Austria Country Profile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 new processes standardised, others updated 1 transparent voting process 48 regular meetings (in total) 1,5 FTEs back office staff funded by the BMWWF for 3 years (01.07.2023-30.06.2025) 	↑
	Diversity We strengthen diversity within the EOSC Support Office Austria.	diversity of partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> qualitative description of the role and relevance of the partners Social Network Analysis (SNA) 	all types	Every third year	Management Board (Chairperson)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> website Austria Country Profile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 new fields of specific expertise: gender balance 44% female, 56% male 	↕
	National Collaboration We build consensus and strengthen collaboration within Austrian institutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> active working groups EOSC SOA working group members EOSC SOA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of groups number of persons (headcounts) 	all types	1 x per year	Secretariat	• colAB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> website newsletter Austria Country Report 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 working groups 32 working group members (in total) 	→
	International Cooperation We increase international cooperation in science and administration.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> staff participating in or chairing EOSC Association Task Forces joint projects with EOSC Association members 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of participants and chairs (headcounts) number of projects 	all types	1 x per year	EOSC Reference Points		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC-A Reports and Monitoring Framework Austria Country Profile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC SOA partners are represented in all 4 new EOSC Association Task Forces via 6 employees 3 joint projects of EOSC SOA partners with EOSC Association members (Skills4EOSC, EOSC Focus, OSTrails) 	↑
	Third-party Funding We increase the third-party funding for EOSC-dedicated e-infrastructures and services.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> partners receiving funding for e-infrastructures and services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of partners funding amount 	all types	1 x per year	FFG / FWF on behalf of the BMWWF or FFG-Monitor Horizon Europe Research Infrastructures	• workshops presentations		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4 EOSC SOA partners received € 2.246.288 funding from the EC (2021-01/2025) 	↑
	Advocacy for EOSC We work closely together with the Austrian ministries and other policy making institutions thus advocating for the EOSC.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> inquiries from politics (e.g. BMWWF) policy advice to streamline the direction of funding calls for the EOSC. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> inquiries from politics (e.g. Parlamentarisches Frühstück) 	all types	1 x per year	Secretariat	• e-mail	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> workshop reports newsletter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 inquiries from politics (BMWWF) 	→

 Scientific Impact
 Socio-economic Impact
 Political Impact

Evolution of KPIs compared with the previous year
 ↑ Ascend ↓ Descend → Stable

Figure 2: EOSC-KPIs: Overview at the SOA-level. CC-BY, credits: Beate Guba (concept), and Juliana de Mello Castro Giroletti (graphic).

Management

Management Board

Starting in July 2024, activities continued as planned, building on those outlined in the previous year's report⁸. Key areas of focus included General Communications, Community Building and Stakeholder Engagement, and Added Value Content. A notable development at the end of the year was a change in the Management Board for the upcoming period. As per the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU), NHMW stepped down from the Board, and CCCA ended its membership in the EOSC Association, resulting in its exclusion from the Board (since only EOSC Association members or observers can hold Board positions). TU Wien and the University of Vienna changed their representatives but remained on the Board.

After the General Assembly in December 2024, the new Management Board (MB) – consisting of Barbara Sanchez Solís (TU Wien, 1st Chair), Michael Feichtinger (University of Vienna), Helmut Klug (University of Graz) and Dimitri Prandner (JKU) – was quick to define the main topics to be focused on during the course of 2025: First, emphasis was to be put on the EOSC EU Node as well as on the establishment of further nodes because they are key to the development of EOSC as a federated system of research infrastructures – or rather a system of federated nodes. The idea was to monitor the development of such nodes closely and to inform the EOSC SOA community on the latest news.

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/13839287>

Second, progress that was made on the European level as well as results of EOSC-related projects were to be shared with the EOSC SOA community more often and in more detail. Thus, it was decided to include more details on the EOSC Association General Assemblies, the yearly EOSC Symposium, etc. in the newsletter. In addition, a new format of communication was introduced. Four times a year, news focusing on only one project, its goals as well as the main deliverables were to be shared with everyone. Projects to be explored in 2025 include OStrails, EOSC Focus, Skills4EOSC and Gravity⁹.

Third, Community Building and Stakeholder Engagement with a focus on four different groups – namely, public universities, federal museums (*Bundesmuseen*), researchers as intended main end users and experts from technical infrastructures, IT support and HPC communities – was to be continued. The groups had distinct objectives: for public universities and federal museums, the focus was on acquiring partners and exchanging information. For researchers, the goal was to identify challenges related to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and open data. As developments within the become more technical, establishing a dialogue with experts from the aforementioned areas was also a key objective. Engagement with IT experts has been temporarily postponed in order to first gather concrete information and lessons learned from the EOSC Nodes, particularly regarding their technical aspects.

As in previous years, the EOSC SOA Secretariat was responsible for drawing a timeline, realizing the objectives and ensuring the implementation of individual work steps – all within a specific time frame. All further details of the activities associated with these areas can therefore be found in the “Secretariat” section below.

Secretariat

In 2024, the team consisted of six members - namely Meghan Bohardt (University of Vienna), Marie Czuray (TU Wien), Katharina Flicker (TU Wien), Stefan Reichmann (Graz University of Technology), Bernd Saurugger (TU Wien) and Birgit Söser (Graz University of Technology). The personnel costs were funded by the previous Ministry for Education, Science and Research¹⁰ (BMBWF).

In this constellation, Katharina Flicker coordinated the EOSC SOA Secretariat. She was also responsible for reporting (e.g. Activity Report, financial report) as well as for Community Building & Stakeholder Engagement (see section “Community Building & Stakeholder Engagement” below). Meghan Bohardt worked particularly in communications. She thus created materials for distribution such as the Knowledge Snacks (see section “Knowledge Snacks” below) and was responsible for the EOSC SOA Newsletter (see section “Newsletter” below). Marie Czuray covered a wide range of activities needed for communications and collected content needed for the website and informational purposes such as calls and events. Stefan Reichmann and Birgit Söser

⁹ Information on Skills4EOSC and Gravity will be shared with the EOSC SOA community outside the actual reporting period – namely in September and towards the end of the year.

¹⁰ <https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/>

co-authored the Knowledge Snacks, initially in collaboration with Meghan Bohardt. Bernd Saurugger managed coLAB and ensured that the mailing lists were regularly updated. He also maintained and updated the website (see section “Website” below) on a regular basis. All other tasks (e.g. writing articles for the Newsletter or minutes) were distributed according to the resources of the team members in the joint meetings, which were held bi-weekly since 2022.

A staff change in the beginning of 2025 led to a slight distribution of the tasks. As Meghan Bohardt left, Marie Czuray took over almost all responsibilities of hers. Stefan Reichmann and Birgit Söser continued to produce bi-monthly Knowledge Snacks. Stefan Reichmann along with Marie Czuray also took up the task of working on News on EOSC-related projects. A team member from the University of Vienna, Sonja Fröschl, joined for six months (January 2025 to June 2025). During that time, she got particularly involved in Community Building & Stakeholder Engagement and in one of the communication formats – that is reporting News on EOSC-related projects.

Website

During this reporting period, further enhancements were made to the EOSC SOA website to improve its structure, content and usability. Building on the previous updates, the focus was on refining the pages and expanding the curated resources to better serve the EOSC SOA community.

One of the main areas of improvement was updating and restructuring important pages such as the homepage, as well as those of the Working Groups and Governance Bodies. These pages now provide clearer and more comprehensive information. Additionally, new resource pages were developed and launched, including:

- [External Resources](#)¹¹ – This page provides a curated collection of valuable materials and references on EOSC, the EOSC Association and the EOSC Federation. It includes external reports, policy documents and PowerPoint slides that facilitate collaboration and knowledge-sharing within the EOSC community.
- [EOSC SOA Materials](#)¹² – This dedicated space contains documents, reports, presentations, and training materials coming from to EOSC SOA Community. It is designed to help users to discover relevant outputs and stay informed about EOSC SOA developments.
- [Hands-On Open Science](#)¹³ – This page offers practical tools for researchers to implement Open Science practices effectively. It contains RDM training courses, and hands-on guides on how to implement Open Science Policies and Communities at institutions.

Additionally, key activities within the EOSC ecosystem were actively promoted. This included highlighting important news, events, open consultations, and funding calls

¹¹ <https://eosc-austria.at/external-resources/>

¹² <https://eosc-austria.at/eosc-soa-materials/>

¹³ <https://eosc-austria.at/hands-on-open-science/>

relevant to the community to foster greater collaboration and engagement among EOSC stakeholders.

Newsletter

To share information efficiently, EOSC SOA communicates via the SOA-all mailing list and newsletter, reaching members, subscribers, and stakeholders directly. The newsletter serves as a crucial communication channel. Published about every two months, it features contributions across the community and aligns with news of the EOSC Association to ensure timely and relevant content. Additionally, it offers readers deeper insights into the evolving Open Science landscape at both national and international levels.

A core objective of the newsletter is to foster a clearer and more approachable understanding of EOSC and its potential impact on Austrian institutions. Since 2025, the EOSC SOA newsletter has also been made available in German, ensuring broader accessibility for the Austrian research community. During the reporting period, five newsletters have been published, which are also available on the EOSC SOA website¹⁴.

Knowledge Snacks

Knowledge Snacks are an ongoing series of one-pagers on topics related to data management. They should not only create useful and quickly digestible content to support research support staff in their daily work – e.g. use cases, best practices, state of the art developments – but also "translate" documents into easily and quickly understandable and readable formats (e.g. guidelines or results of EOSC task forces and projects).

In the reporting period, this series has produced eight editions (see *Figure 3*), covering topics such as "What is a PID?", "The FAIR Principles", "Some common misconceptions about FAIR", "Open Data", "CARE Principles", "FAIR - CARE - Open" and "machine-actionable DMPs". The Knowledge Snacks are published on Zenodo and referenced in Phaidra Open Educational Resources Hub, the respective citation and additional reading material can be found in the EOSC Support Office Austria Zotero Group. All Knowledge Snacks can also be viewed and downloaded on the EOSC SOA Website¹⁵.

¹⁴ See Newsletters #8 to #12: <https://eosc-austria.at/newsletter/>

¹⁵ <https://eosc-austria.at/eosc-soa-materials/>

Figure 3: Examples of published Knowledge Snacks.

News on EOSC-related projects

To increase the visibility of EOSC-related projects and make their developments more accessible, a new reporting format has been introduced within EOSC SOA. As a low-threshold communication tool, this report is published on a regular basis and aims to inform the Austrian research community about key developments, contributions, and impacts of these projects.

A key focus of these reports is to highlight Austria's role and contributions within each project, as well as their implications for the local research community. Additionally, they aim to present key facts and may include visual elements, such as snippets from existing project posters – these summarize key information and help convey the main messages concisely.

The reports are published four times a year, starting with OStrails (March), followed by EOSC Focus (June), Skills4EOSC (expected in September), and EOSC Gravity (expected in December). These updates are distributed via the EOSC SOA-all Mailing List, not limited to the newsletter subscribers, as this format serves a different communication purpose.

EOSC Support Office Austria

The EOSC Support Office Austria (EOSC SOA) supports ACONET, which is the Austrian EOSC Mandated Organization, and all Austrian research institutions. The goal of EOSC SOA is to realize the EOSC vision: a federated, multi-disciplinary environment to find and use data, tools, and services for research, innovation, and education.

WHO ARE WE?

EOSC SOA is a **collaboration** of diverse institutions, agreeing via a Memorandum of Understanding, to **integrate Austria's research infrastructure** into the European landscape.

Our Objectives:

1. Coordinate Austrian contributions in the implementation of EOSC.
2. Influence Austria's strategic EOSC agenda.
3. Foster "EOSC Readiness" at partner institutions.

All Austrian institutions are welcome to join us:

WHAT DO WE OFFER?

We support **Austria's active engagement** in the development and realization of EOSC by:

- Harmonizing developments and **building an EOSC community** through national and international networking.
- Providing guidelines and good practices for the **establishment of EOSC**.
- Connecting researchers, infrastructure providers, and management to **develop and operate EOSC services**.
- Synchronizing on the steps required to **participate in the EOSC Federation** and establishing an EOSC Node.
- Updating on developments, **funding and collaboration** opportunities.
- **Collecting requirements** from institutions, service providers, and researchers to shape the evolution of EOSC.
- **Aligning efforts** with other Mandated Organizations.

Subscribe to the EOSC SOA Newsletter, join our webinars and Working Groups, take a look at our Zenodo Community (EOSC Austria) and meet us at the EOSC Café. Let us know your expectations, concerns, and needs to help us jointly build EOSC.

www.eosc-austria.at
contact@eosc-austria.at

The reports have a standardized layout that aligns with the EOSC SOA branding. In addition to an English version, a German version is provided. To ensure accessibility for a broad audience, the reports are written in clear and straightforward language, avoiding complex project terminology wherever possible.

Community Building & Stakeholder Engagement

With respect to Community Building & Stakeholder Engagement this year's activities focus on public universities, federal museums (Bundesmuseen), researchers and experts from technical infrastructures, IT support and HPC-communities. In the first half of the year, the focus was on public universities and federal museums with the aim of acquiring partners. To be able to systematically recruit them, tables listing all potential new partners were drawn up and people responsible for the respective institution were appointed. Information materials for these stakeholders were also updated and drafted¹⁶. Activities aimed at establishing a dialogue with experts from technical infrastructures, IT support and HPC communities as well as with researchers were not initiated until July 2025.

As in the previous year, communication and information flows with the EOSC SOA Reference Points were maintained. Four times a year – in September and December 2024 as well as in March and June 2025 – they received information by email on relevant events and calls, results from projects, the EOSC Association's Task Forces and EOSC SOA Working Groups.

Work also continued in connection with events as EOSC SOA partners participated in, and/or (co-) organized numerous events:

- [Bringing EOSC Task Force Outcomes to the Austrian Research Data Management Community](#)¹⁷ (October 2024): Members from three of the 13 previous EOSC Association Task Forces were invited to share results with the EOSC SOA community. This webinar was organized by the EOSC SOA Secretariat.
- [EOSC Symposium 2024](#)¹⁸ (October 2024): EOSC SOA partners took part in the EOSC Symposium 2024 in Berlin, Germany. The focus of this event was on the presentation of the EOSC EU Node and the development steps of the EOSC after 2027.
- [EOSC Association General Assembly](#) (November 2024): The 9th General Assembly was held online to lay the foundations for next year's activities. A full wrap up article¹⁹ summarizing key issues was provided by the EOSC Association.

¹⁶ See 1-pager summarizing benefits (<https://eosc-austria.at/join/>) and informational slides in German (https://eosc-austria.at/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/EOSC_SOA_German_Version.pdf) and English (https://eosc-austria.at/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/20250414_EOSC_SOA_En.pdf).

¹⁷ <https://eosc-austria.at/events/bringing-task-force-outcomes-to-the-eosc-soa-community/>

¹⁸ <https://eosc.eu/symposium2024/>

¹⁹ <https://eosc.eu/news/2024/12/ready-for-2025-9th-general-assembly-prepares-eosc-a-for-defining-year-ahead/>

- [Symposium Cluster Forschungsdaten](#) (January 2025): The Secretariat created a poster²⁰ (see *Figure 4*), which was displayed during the event in order to increase the awareness of EOSC SOA activities.
- [TU Wien Netzwerkmesse](#) (February 2025): The poster (see *Figure 4*) was also put up here. Members of the Secretariat also presented the EOSC SOA (Focus: Who are we? What do we do?) in a lightning talk.
- [AG Open Science der Bundesmuseen in Österreich](#) (March 2025): Katrin Vohland (NHMW) invited the members of the Working Group from the Austrian Federal Museums to discuss the Impact of AI in their daily working lives. Additionally, a member from the EOSC SOA Secretariat introduced the EOSC SOA and opened a discussion of potential synergies.
- [2nd Austrian Library Congress](#)²¹ (March 2025): The EOSC SOA Working Group Researcher Engagement in Austria presented their work in a session called "Open Science Kooperation".
- [Die Bedeutung von wissenschaftlichen Sammlungen und Open Science Kompetenzen für Politik, Kultur, Wissenschaft und Kunst in Österreich](#)²² (April 2025): Aiming at a broad audience from politics, management, and science, the Natural History Museum Vienna (NHMW) and members of the EOSC SOA organized a webinar to discuss Open Science in Austria and Europe within the framework of the project Skills4EOSC.
- [STS Conference Graz](#) (May 2025): The Working Group Researcher Engagement in Austria participated by presenting their research's results during the session "What's next? Challenges of Digital Research Practices, Academic Communication and Shared Research Infrastructures put into Perspective". Further information on the content can be found in the already published Book of Abstracts²³.
- [Kulturpool Stakeholder Forum](#) (May 2025): The "Kulturpool" is a portal as well as a competency center for cultural digital heritage, hosted by the NHMW. Two EOSC SOA partners – namely the TU Wien and the NHMW – were represented in the annual Stakeholder Forum, in 2025 held at Ars Electronica, Linz. EOSC SOA was introduced in a panel discussion, in the context of debating the relevance of European infrastructures and collaboration platforms²⁴.
- [Research Data Day & EOSC national Tripartite Event](#)²⁵ (May 2025): The event took place in Brno, Czech Republic. Dedicated to research data management and EOSC, the event brought together over 200 participants representing a broad range of institutions from across Europe. The program included lectures, panel discussions, and hands-on workshops, with a central theme for preparing data for

²⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/14745686>

²¹ <https://www.bibliothekskongress.at/>

²² <https://eosc-austria.at/webinar-recap-open-science-and-scientific-collections-in-austria/>

²³ <https://openlib.tugraz.at/download.php?id=68147d4730594&location=browse>

²⁴ <https://info.kulturpool.at/stakeholder-forum-2025/>

²⁵ <https://www.eosc.cz/en/news-and-events/events-calendar/national-tripartite-event-cz-25>

AI. In addition, the event served as a platform to showcase the ongoing progress in the implementation of EOSC. EOSC SOA was represented by TU Graz and TU Wien and joined an informal meeting with the EOSC CZ Secretariat.

- [EOSC Association General Assembly](#)²⁶ (May 2025): In addition to the regular agenda (including status updates, audits, and the formal admission of new members and observers) a new president was elected. This General Assembly also coincided with the closing event of the EOSC Focus project and the kick-off meeting of the EOSC Gravity project. Representatives from EOSC SOA participated not only in the General Assembly but also actively contributed to both project meetings.
- Participation in [further events](#) such as “Info-Share” events with selected Mandated Organizations (organized by SWITCH and ETH Zürich), first dialogue meetings with shortlisted candidate nodes and webinars organized by the EOSC Association on the progress of the build-up phase and related opportunities (see section “Activities related to the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation” for details).

Publications

Two articles providing information about EOSC SOA were published. The first article “Advancing Research: The Role of the EOSC and EOSC Support Office Austria”²⁷ was published in October 2024 as part of ERCIM News. The vision of the EOSC and the EOSC SOA as well as its activities, such as the EOSC Café and the Working Groups, were introduced to a broader audience.

At the request of the ACONET Association, the Secretariat also wrote a short article to report on EOSC SOA activities in the last period in the context of the Association’s annual report. In addition to this, the opportunity was also taken to provide information on the structure of the EOSC SOA and an outlook on planned activities and future developments regarding the establishment of the EOSC Nodes²⁸.

Three papers were submitted in peer-reviewed journals to introduce EOSC (SOA) to a broader audience and thereby increase awareness and emphasize its relevance to the Austrian and European research landscape. One of the papers was published after the reporting period²⁹, another has been accepted but is not yet published at the time of writing, and the third remains under review.

²⁶ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-association/general-assembly-meetings/>

²⁷ <https://ercim-news.ercim.eu/en139/r-i/advancing-research-the-role-of-the-eosc-and-eosc-support-office-austria>

²⁸ Flicker, Katharina (April 2025). EOSC Support Office Austria: Erfolgreiche Aktivitäten und Impulse für die europäische Forschungslandschaft, in ACONET Verein (Eds.) Jahresbericht 2024: 44-47. <https://www.aco.net/jahresberichte>

²⁹ The Chair of the EOSC SOA General Assembly, together with members of the Management Board and the Secretariat, co-authored the article “Adopting EOSC on the Ground – Integrating (European) Research infrastructure into national institutions”: <https://www.degruyterbrill.com/document/doi/10.1515/abitech-2025-0059/html>

Apart from that, there are numerous publications from the EOSC SOA Community that have been published on Zenodo as part of the EOSC Austria Community³⁰. These include, for example, the results of the Working Groups, the already described Knowledge Snacks and short news articles.

Synergy Team

The Synergy Team is made up of the coordinators of the Working Groups (WGs) and the Chair of the Management Board (MB). As of the last General Assembly in December 2025, all WGs except the WG Researcher Engagement in Austria concluded their activities, resulting in no appointed Synergy Team spokespersons. The coordinator of the remaining WG and the Chair of the MB continue to share updates on an ad hoc basis to ensure ongoing information flow. The WGs that concluded include Austria Country Report, Collections, Technical Infrastructure, and Training.

Thus, comprehensive information on the activities and outcomes of the WGs from July 2024 to December 2025 is presented in the 'Working Groups' section. Exceptions are the WG Collection and the WG Technical Infrastructure, which did not report any activities during this period.

Although the WG Training officially concluded at the EOSC SOA General Assembly in December 2024, it continued certain activities beyond that point. As a result, both the WG Researcher Engagement in Austria and the WG Training have provided reports covering their activities from January 2025 to June 2025.

Working Groups

Austria Country Report

The WG Austria Country Report actively monitored the development of EOSC-related processes in Austria throughout its operational period (2021–2024), with a focus on open science and FAIR-related policies, projects, activities, and research data (management) infrastructures. During the reporting period (July 2024 to June 2025), two reports were published on Zenodo and consequently shared with the EOSC SOA community:

- Austria Country Profile Q3/2024 (published on 30 September 2024):
<https://zenodo.org/records/13860938>
- Austria Country Profile Q2/2024 (published on 2 July 2024):
<https://zenodo.org/records/12624049>

Researcher Engagement in Austria

The WG Researcher Engagement in Austria was established in late 2021. From the very beginning, the idea was to better understand actual research practices (including the handling, sharing and reuse of data) across disciplines and – using this as a starting point – discuss issues of trust in data (quality) as well as in results. The first year was used to define

the exact research agenda as well as a timeline. An interview guideline comprised exclusively of open questions was created. The process of identifying interview participants at public universities in Austria was subsequently initiated. Additionally, a list of all public universities in Austria was compiled to be able to systematically contact researchers. This list was later reused by the EOSC SOA Secretariat as part of the Community Building and Stakeholder Engagement.

In the second year the focus was primarily on conducting the interviews as well as on follow-up activities such as transcribing and editing the interviews, so that shortened versions could be published on Zenodo³¹ and shared with the EOSC SOA Community. All interviews were edited and published only with the explicit consent of the interviewees. It should also be emphasized at this point that the total of 12 interviews made it possible to reach researchers from mathematics, computer sciences, life sciences, social sciences and humanities at 10 of 23 public universities. The public universities in the following federal states³² (*Bundesländer*) were fully covered: Carinthia, Lower Austria and Tyrol.

Although the final interviews were conducted and published in the third year, the primary focus shifted towards analyzing the interview transcripts and preparing for potential conference submissions. In 2025, the fourth year, the results of the working group were presented at the 2. *Österreichischer Bibliothekskongress*³³ in Vienna in March and at the *STS Conference*³⁴ in Graz in May. The Working Group on Researcher Engagement in Austria concluded its activities with the submission of two related articles in June 2025. It will not extend its activities beyond the current period.

Training

The WG Training has set itself the task of focusing on newcomers to the field of research data management. The first step was to see how training materials, especially those written in German, could be reused. The collection of materials on training courses in research data management at the Berlin State Library provides a good basis for this because not only can openly and freely available materials be uploaded and described in great detail, the metadata is also curated by experts. It is also possible to link training material that is already available in repositories and describe it.

In a further step, a list of mainly German-language articles, texts and websites was compiled to help people new to research data management get an overview. Each literature citation and reference to a link was summarised in a paragraph. Different aspects of research data management were addressed, and various research orientations were considered.

³¹ All interviews can be viewed and downloaded on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/wgreaeoscsoa/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

³² Note: There are no public universities in *Vorarlberg* and *Burgenland*.

³³ <https://www.bibliothekskongress.at/>

³⁴ <https://stsconf.tugraz.at/>

This was a subjective selection, but one that had already proven to be very useful in practice. This compilation of helpful links and literature will soon be published as open access in “Mitteilungen der Vereinigung Österreichischer Bibliothekarinnen und Bibliothekare” and can be used for training and continuing professional development programmes.

EOSC Café

The EOSC Café is an open forum composed of experts from both within and outside the EOSC initiative, representing diverse backgrounds in science and research, research policy, society, and the economy. These experts offer external perspectives and strategic input to the EOSC SOA. During the reporting period, the EOSC Café convened twice – in December 2024 and April 2025. The December 2024 in-person meeting focused on initial activities around the EOSC Federation build-up phase. Consequently, discussions focused on key developments (such as the publication of the EOSC Federation Handbook³⁵ or the so-called Candidate Nodes³⁶) and future perspectives related to this evolving landscape. The meeting on 8 April 2025 focused on recent developments in the first wave of the EOSC Federation build-up phase, including the establishment of the build-up Group, and addressed the implications for the Austrian EOSC initiative.

³⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/14999577>

³⁶ <https://eosc.eu/news/eoscs-build-up-phase-to-begin-with-march-kick-off/>

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